

International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Scientific Research (IJAESR)

ISSN: 2349 -3607 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 -4824 (Print)

Available online at:

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-4-aug-2014>

Email: editor@arseam.com

Instructions for authors and subscription information:

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COLLISION AVOIDANCE SYSTEM USING ANDROID DEVICE VIA BLUETOOTH

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Abstract

Collision Avoidance Systems, this is an alternative step to avoid collision, are one of the great challenges in the area of active safety for road vehicles. In India the total annual deaths due to road accidents has crossed 1.18 lakhs, according to the latest report of National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB). If these deficiencies are not controlled at early stages they might cause huge economical problems affecting the road side networks. The main part of the work was to carry out a feasibility study on vehicle collision avoidance system using wireless sensor networks. The collision avoidance can be done by Ultrasonic ping sensor. Vehicle collision avoidance system can be identified by using Ultrasonic sensor which will be connected to the car at four sides with the LCD and to an Android mobile (via Bluetooth) to show the top view of the car. Initially in our previous part [5] we had our embedded systems where we had shown the collision detection using the Ultra Sonic Sensors [4] and an LCD display.

Key words: NCRB, LCD, Blue tooth, Android

I. INTRODUCTION

As we all know that android is the operating system that is used widely in the world without any problem and is free. Now we thought of some serious problems in society and decided to develop something that would be beneficial to our society and helpful to reduce the road accidents too.

As per our Embedded System we just need some something that could be connected to our android phones. To connect the embedded systems and android we can have

- Infrared connection, we cannot use this because it doesn't support a long distance

- Wired connection, we cannot use this too because if we use the usb there can be problem of loose connection.
- Bluetooth connection, we can use this because it can be easily connected to our embedded and we will be having a Bluetooth in our android phones from beginning there is no problem of loose connection or the distance, Bluetooth supports a certain distance that can be perfect.

Android (Operating System)

Android is an operating system based on Linux Kernel. These devices can also be known as smart phones or tablet computers. Android is held by the OHA (Open Handset Alliance). This is the group of companies who have the license to get the Android source codes. The companies like Samsung, HTC, Micromax etc.

Android Basics

Android is the name of operating system (OS) developed by Open Handset Alliance (OHA). Android is known as the software stack for mobile devices that includes a middleware, operating system and key applications.[2.] Open development platform offers Android developers the capability to build extremely rich and innovative applications. Developers around the world are welcome to take benefit of the hardware devices, background services, alarms, access location information, add notifications to the status bar and many other features.

Android Bluetooth

[3.]Bluetooth is a technology that is simple and secures any where we use.The key features of Bluetooth technology are low power and low cost for implementation. The Bluetooth Specification defines a uniform structure for a wide range of devices to connect and communicate with each other easily.

Bluetooth is the better solution for both the Infrared and Wired connections. It provides authenticity to the user.

Bluetooth Methods and Description

- Enabled
- Discoverable
- IsEnabled
- Disabled

Enabled:

This helps us to enable or turn on the Bluetooth of our android phone.

Discoverable:

This is helpful to make the Bluetooth discoverable or visible to other device for 120 seconds.

IsEnabled:

This is useful when our Bluetooth is already on and again we are trying to switch on the Bluetooth of our phone.

Disable:

This will turn off the Bluetooth of our phone.

Bluetooth Permissions

Android provides BluetoothAdapter class to communicate with Bluetooth. Create an object of this calling by calling the static method getDefaultAdapter(). Its syntax is given below.

```
privateBluetoothAdapter BA;  
  
BA=BluetoothAdapter.getDefaultAdapter();
```

In order to enable the Bluetooth of your device, call the intent with the following Bluetoothconstant **ACTION_REQUEST_ENABLE**.

Its syntax is.

```
Intent turnOn = new Intent(BluetoothAdapter.ACTION_REQUEST_ENABLE);  
  
startActivityForResult(turnOn, 0);
```

II. REQUIREMENTS

Eclipse Indigo (IDE)

Eclipse is an Integrated Development Environment (IDE). It contains a based workspace and an extensible plug-in system for customizing the environment. Eclipse SDK is free and open source software written mostly in Java, Eclipse can be used to develop applications. By means of various plug-ins, Eclipse may also be used to develop applications in other programming languages like Ada, ABAP, C, C++, COBOL, It can also be used to develop packages for the software Mathematica. Development environments include the Eclipse Java development tools (JDT) for Java and Scala, Eclipse CDT for C/C++ and Eclipse PDT for PHP, among others.

Java Development Kit 6

The Java Development Kit (JDK) is an execution of the Java EE Java ME or Java SE platforms released by Oracle Corporation in the form of a binary product aimed at Java developers on Solaris, Linux, Windows or Mac OS X. Since the overview of the Java platform, it has become the most widely used Software Development Kit (SDK).

Android application development.

In this section[1.] we will discuss about how to develop an android projects.

Before we start this , we need to:

1. Download the Android SDK.
2. Install the ADT plugin for Eclipse (if you'll use the Eclipse IDE).
3. Download the latest SDK tools and platforms using the SDK Manager.

In this part we will show you how to create an android app we are showing an example of creation of android app i.e. how to create an android app

1. For creating new project click on the File -> New -> Project.

It opens the new wizard window where you can select application template and set the name of the project and package name.

On the click on Next Button, it moves to the next step. Here provide the “Application Name”, “Project Name” and “Package Name”. “Package Name” is a same as “Name Space” in .Net and it must be unique. The project name is only used by Eclipse and it must be unique in the workspace.

You also need to select “Minimum Required SDK” from dropdown. It is the lowest version of Android that your application will support. Then select “Target SDK” which is the Highest API that the application is known to work with. Then select the installed SDK for “Compile With” option to compile your code for selected targeted SDK.

In the next steps of the wizard, you need to select icons, some other information and on the last step provide the name of your activity and it's Navigation Type.

I will provide the detail of activity and layout later, for now you can say it is window’s form as desktop application or as a Web page in web application. Provide the name of Activity and Layout. Leave Navigation type “None” for now. Press finish button. Eclipse will automatically generate start up activity for you.

Within the Eclipse, you can see your project in the “Package Explorer” pane of the left-hand side of the screen. The “HelloWorld” application contains several auto generated folders and file. Let’s discuss it one by one.

- **/Src:** It contains the all java source files those are associated to the project. For example the MainActivity.java file generated by Eclipse is stored in this directory under the package name “com.MyFirst.helloworld” you specified in the wizard. You can add more packages for your application e.g. com.MyFirst.Fragments, CommonClasses etc.
- **/gen:** It contains the java source files and other code files generated by Eclipse. We will use R.java file code later in our project. This file is generated to link your resource files for use in your java files in /src folder.

III. RUN YOUR APPLICATION IN EMULATOR

- First you need to configure emulator for testing your application. To configure your emulator click on window -> Android Virtual Device Manager

It will open pop up where you can create new Virtual device, Edit exist and start any virtual device. After create your new virtual device close this window. Now right click on the application in “Package Explorer” pane on the left-hand side of the screen and click on Run As -> Android Application. It will compile your application and execute it in the emulator.

After a few minutes the emulator will be started and you will be able to see your HelloWorld application in it.

On the screen you can see Status Bar, Action Bar and Navigation Bar. You have nothing to do with the Status Bar and Navigation Bar, it is being managed by System. The Action bar contains the logo and title of your application and you can also open menu by click Menu button (three vertical dots) on it. Layout Area where we place all UI controls.

IV. DESIGN LAYOUT

As it is mentioned earlier Eclipse generates by default one layout. In emulator the application is showing only “Hello World!” text in the middle of the screen. Open the layout from /res/layout/activity_main.xml and you can see the layout in designer in the middle area Eclipse. You can change view from graphic or xml as per your wish. Eclipse provides you both option in the bottom of the layout “Graphical Layout” or “activity_main.xml”.

V. TESTING

1. The diagram below shows the embedded part with distance in the LCD.

2. This figure shows the user interface in an Android smart phone which means the red zone is danger zone and the green zone is safe zone detected by Ultrasonic sensor.

3. The figure below shows the integration of both the embedded part and the android application as we can see both the things working.

VI. REFERENCES

WEB REFERENCE

1. <http://www.vogella.com/tutorials/android.html>
2. <http://developer.android.com/training/index.html>
3. <http://developer.android.com/reference/android/bluetooth/package-summary.html>
4. <http://www.vogella.com/tutorials/AndroidSensor/article.html>
5. American International Journal of Research in Science, Technology, Engineering & Mathematics, ISSN(Print):2328-3491, ISSN(Online): 2328-3580, ISSN(CD-ROM): 2328-3629, Issue 6, Volume 1 & 2, March-May, 2014
Paper ID #: AIJRSTEM 14-313
Title: COLLISION AVOIDANCE SCHEME USING EMBEDDED SYSTEM
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